

PARTICIPATION OF RURAL WOMEN FOR EFFECTIVE AND SUSTAINABLE FOOD CROP PRODUCTION AND IMPROVED INCOME GENERATION IN NIGERIA

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Abstract: *The paper reviews the participation of rural women for effective and sustainable food crop production and improved income generation in Nigeria. It begins with sustainable agricultural production, representing a broad spectrum of agricultural methodology, which supports the environment. This is followed by the strategies for sustainable agricultural production, which extends to food crops production strategies. In Nigeria, women were found to produce over 80 percent of her food products despite their responsibilities for household work; they were found to know they could produce most of the food. Increase in yields on their women's farms could increase by 20 to 30 percent if women had the same access to productive resources as men, thereby raising total agricultural output in developing countries by 2.5 to 4 percent, which could in turn reduce the number of hungry people in the world by 12 to 17 percent. Worldwide, women produce over 50 per cent of all food grown and in most of the developing nations, Nigeria inclusive, the face of farming is female. The major food crops produced by women include beans, sesame, cassava, groundnuts, maize (corn), melon, millet, rice, sorghum, soybeans and yams. It is imperative, therefore, to encourage the participation of rural women for effective and sustainable food crop production and improved income generation in Nigeria.*

INTRODUCTION

Background to the Study

Agriculture constitutes the main source of livelihood and employment opportunity for high proportion of people in Africa (Rafael, 2023). In Nigeria, it serves as the major source of income for approximately 70 to 80% of the population

which crop sub-sector remains the major driver accounting for about 92% overall nominal growth of the agricultural sector. Generally, agriculture contributed 20.85% to Gross Domestic Product (GDP) in 2017 (National Bureau of Statistics (NBS), 2018). The importance of women and their role in

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sustainable food crop farming, sustenance of food security and income generation, cannot be over-emphasized. According to Food and Agriculture Organization (FAO) (2009), women in Nigeria provide between 60 to 80% of the food crops like yam, maize, sorghum, millet, cowpea and soybeans for household consumption.

However, effective and efficient execution of household and farm roles by women requires quick access to farm and off-farm resources, which is usually not the case because of social and technical constraints (Rafael, 2023). Studies have shown that to increase productivity and profitability of food crops, there is need to utilize sustainable production strategies or practices that are environmentally friendly (FAO, 2017). These comprise crop intensification through the use of fertilizers, pesticides, improved crop varieties and irrigation facilities, Climate-Smart practices to help mitigate climate change and conservative farming through low or zero tillage, cover crops and crop rotation.

Sustainable crop production intensification is an eco-friendly approach to farming that helps to achieve higher yields needed while enhancing and protecting natural resources (FAO, 2017). It promotes agricultural management practices, such as conservation agriculture which includes minimum soil disturbance, permanent soil cover and increased on-farm species diversity. It supports the sustainable use of plant genetic resources through the use of quality seeds of adapted varieties and also provides assistance to farmers for efficient use of inputs such as

fertilizer and water for maintaining healthy soils.

Women play an increasingly greater role in agriculture (Okafor, 2015). Ensuring equal opportunities to those of men in transforming agriculture is a prerequisite for sustainable intensification. Increased gender equity in agriculture is both a practical and a social justice issue: practical because women are responsible for much of the production by smallholders; and social justice because in many cases they currently do not have rights over land and water resources, or full access to markets, and often they do not even control the crops they produce.

Strategies to promote gender equity must be tailored carefully to the social and economic context. Ownership of assets is very important for achieving sustainable intensification of agriculture (SIA) and poverty reduction especially among women (CGIAR, 2017). Women's control of assets is associated with positive development outcomes at the household and individual levels; thus, they need to adopt sustainable production strategies that will increase their food crops production.

Problem Statement

Sustainable food production is one of the major challenges of the twenty-first century (Singh and Singh, 2017). According to World Bank (2018), world population is expected to grow by over a third in 2050 implying that market demand for food will continue to grow. The projection shows that feeding a population of 9.1 billion people in 2050 would require raising overall food production to 70% particularly in

Nigeria where the population is expected to double. In many developing countries like Nigeria, the restriction of women in agriculture access to production resources has further exacerbated food insecurity.

Men are presumed dominant gender in agricultural production, but the role of women in food crops production cannot be over-emphasized. About 60–80% of rural women in Nigeria, are found to produce two-third of the food (Okafor, 2015), but they are constraint with problem of sustainability as most of them lack access to production inputs and good management practices. Therefore, effective, efficient and sustainable strategies need to be adopted to increase food crops production. There exists wide gap between food production and demand, as well as a striking relationship between production and income generation.

To increase food production in sustainable manner, appropriate strategy for sustainable development needs to be adopted. Increase in food production will lead to increase in income for the rural women. But most rural women are constraint with production resources and cultural barriers. Those that have production resources are most often not motivated as they do not participate in most agricultural development programmes.

Thus, for increased food crops production, women farmers need innovative technologies, improved crop varieties and sustainable farming practices such as intensive cropping, conservative agriculture, climate-smart adaptation among others. Most studies on sustainable agriculture had focused on soil

conservation and water management in eco-friendly environment, little or no studies have been carried out to determine its effectiveness on food crop production. While conceiving the need to study the effectiveness of sustainable food crop production strategies, it is essential to appraise existing works with a view to establish the need to consider the involvement of the rural women to improve their food crops production and income. Therefore, this paper reviews the participation of rural women for effective and sustainable food crop production and improved income generation in Nigeria.

METHODOLOGY

Sustainable agricultural production

Sustainable agriculture is a recent concept that had evolved in great earnest in the last two decades or so. Sustainable agriculture is essential to meet the increasing demand for food, climate change, degradation of the ecosystem and sustain the global competitiveness of a country's food production system (Aneke, *et al.*, 2025). The concept of sustainable agriculture has now increase support and acceptance, as it may be a way to address many environmental and social concerns. Essentially, sustainable agriculture integrates three main objectives which are: (i) economic sustainability and profitability, (ii) environmental concerns and (iii) social acceptability (Jovovic *et al.*, 2017). Hopefully it can provide new and innovative as well as economically viable opportunities for farmers, researchers, consumers, policy makers and others in the food production arena.

Sustainable food production is one of the major challenges of the twenty first century in the era of global environmental problems such as climate change, increasing population and natural resource degradation including soil degradation and bio-diversity loss (Singh and Singh, 2017). Traditional agriculture is getting increased attention worldwide in context of sustainable food production in changing climate. Okadi and Agu (2023) reviewed the strategies for promoting sustainable agricultural production and family food security in Nigeria. A literature search was conducted through databases such as Scopus, ISI Web of Knowledge, google scholar, directory of open access journal (DOAJ), and research gate. Depending on the context, improved performance may mean any or all of the following: increased productivity and profitability, enhanced use of local resources, maximized returns from external inputs, improved stability and diversity of yields, reduced greenhouse gas emissions, enhanced ecological resilience and environmental service provision.

There are still significant yield gaps in some world regions that can be exploited through simple interventions such as better seed, nutrients, and water management (Mueller, 2012). However, it is generally necessary to move towards more sophisticated, more knowledge intensive forms of agriculture and provide the technologies and incentives that make it viable for farmers to adopt and adapt them.

In crop production, agro-ecological intensification primarily implies to implement good agronomic management principles in a local context. According to Dobermann and Nelson (2013), intensification of agriculture has been the driving force behind the rapid growth of food supplies globally. The success of food production in reducing hunger and improving nutrition globally is also the result of a variety of factors. These include the increased use of fertilizer, water, pesticides, drugs, new crop varieties and animal breeds and innovative agriculture practices such as climate-smart practice (Kinuthia *et al.*, 2016). Achieving the transition to sustainable agricultural development requires a vision that radically rethinks the status-quo.

Food and Agriculture Organization (FAO) (2017) posited that sustainable agriculture lies at the core of the 2030 Agenda. Sustainable agriculture plays a critical role in reducing poverty through pro-poor approaches that encompass family farming, women and youth empowerment, value chain, market access and social protection schemes.

Sustainable agricultural production strategies

Sustainable production of safe and nutritious food is critical to the welfare of all people in the country. Sustainable agriculture contributes to food security of most developing nation (Beddington, 2010). Environmental sustainability is a major driving force for the development and adoption of sustainable farming practices where monoculture production of agriculture and forestry

commodities have led to reduced biodiversity and loss of wildlife habitat, increased non-point source pollution of ground and surface water, and deterioration of family farms (Jose and Gordon, 2008).

Climate-Smart Agriculture (CSA) is a sustainable agricultural production strategy based on the objectives of sustainably enhancing food production, climate adaptation and resilience, and reduction in green house emission (FAO, 2010). Soil health and fertility, climate change and variation, biodiversity loss, pollution, environmental dilapidation, and plant and animal diseases are some food systems disturbances that affect food security. A systematic review of 152 published literature from Google, Google Scholar, and Web of Science databases revealed that the challenges impacting food production and food systems sustainability include an expanding population, competition for resources, the complexity of the global food chain, climate change, communicable diseases, and other biological hazards (Emeka, 2025).

The CSA approach has three objectives which are to: sustainably enhance agricultural productivity to support equitable increase in income, food security and development; increasing adaptive capacity and resilience to shocks at multiple levels, from farm to national and reducing green-house emissions and increasing carbon sequestration where possible. Sustainable food production while reducing green-house emissions and increasing climate resilience of agricultural system is the foremost

objective of CSA (Harvey *et al.*, 2014; Brandt *et al.*, 2015).

Traditional agro-ecosystems are receiving rising attention as sustainable alternatives to industrial farming (Fraser *et al.*, 2015). Traditional agriculture is getting increased considerations for bio-diversity conservation and sustainable food production in changing climate. Padmavathy and Poyyamoli (2011) reported that India has a longer heritage tradition of sustainable natural and organic farming strategies most of which until recently were not properly documented. The country with its rich diversity of ecosystems, soil types and monsoon patterns has evolved a wide variety of alternative farming techniques to suit its local diversity.

According to Rigueiro *et al.* (2008), the different forms of sustainable agriculture include organic farming, bio-dynamic farming, zero tillage farming, urban and Peri-urban farming, natural farming, eco-farming, permaculture, poly-culture, integrated farming system and floating farming. These are the predominant potential sustainable farming techniques practiced in various parts of the world.

Sustainable food crops production strategies

Society is making increasingly stringent demands on agriculture which includes adapting to resource scarcity, coping with an unstable climate and meeting expanding needs for ecosystem services that begin with food production and beyond (Ray and Shaffer, 2014). In the face of a growing global population and

the unpredictable impacts of climate change, strategies for resilient crop production and productivity have become paramount in agriculture. In Vincent (2023), a range of innovative and proven approaches aimed at bolstering crop resilience while optimizing productivity was explored. These strategies encompass diverse crop rotations, conservation agriculture, water management, climate-resilient crop varieties, integrated pest management, organic farming practices, agroforestry, data-driven decision-making, risk management, and ongoing education and training.

Over the past decade, there have been several efforts to promote sustainable intensification of smallholder farming systems (Barnes *et al.*, 2016). Several sustainable agricultural strategies include conservation tillage, soil and water conservation, legume crop rotations, improved seed varieties and use of animal manure (Kassie *et al.*, 2013). These have been promoted by research and development organizations to promote climate-smart agriculture, restore soil health and bolster resilience of small holder farming systems. Yet, the adoption of conservation practices is lagging among small holder farmers in many parts of the world (Wollni *et al.*, 2010).

Traditional agro-eco-systems are receiving rising attention as sustainable alternatives to industrial farming (Fraser *et al.*, 2015). They are getting increased considerations for biodiversity conservation and sustainable food production in changing climate. Agroforestry, intercropping, crop rotation, cover cropping,

organic composting and integrated crop-animal farming are prominent sustainable agricultural strategies. These traditional food crops production strategies are advocated as a model for climate-smart in agriculture and they are presented as follows:

Agro-forestry is widely adopted as a climate-smart practice due to its potentials for climate change mitigation, adaptation, crop productivity and food security (Coulibaly *et al.*, 2017). It is practiced worldwide as a land-use management system but widespread in tropical regions. Agro-forestry enhances soil organic matter, agriculture productivity, carbon sequestration, water retention, agro-biodiversity and farmers' income (Paul *et al.*, 2017).

Inter-cropping is the practice of cultivating more than one crop species on the same field. It is one of the highly productive farming systems (Hu *et al.*, 2017). Intercropping reduces the climate-driven crop failure as variety of crops have different climatic adaptability and efficiently utilize the natural resources such as land, light, water and nutrient for increase biodiversity, productivity, resilience and stability of agro-ecosystem (Ning *et al.*, 2017).

Wheat–maize intercropping combined with conservation agricultural practices can be used for reducing carbon-dioxide emission and increasing crop productivity (Hu *et al.*, 2017). Legume intercropping helps in reducing the external input of nitrogen fertilizers. Intercropping of maize with legumes reduces nitrate leaching and synthetic fertilizers input and enhances agro-biodiversity, soil health and crop yield (von Cossel *et al.*, 2017). It enhances

the availability of nutrients (nitrogen and phosphorus), crop growth and nutrient use efficiency.

Crop rotation is another food crops production strategy which refers to the practice of growing a sequence of plant species on the same land. It is an ancient practice that has been used for thousands of years and been recaptured the global attention to solve the increasing agro-ecological problems such as declining soil quality and climate change resulting from short rotation (Liu *et al.*, 2016). Crop rotation is a sustainable approach that increases yield and water use efficiency while reducing soil erosion. It is an effective approach for carbon sequestration as compared to growing same type of crop continuously (Triberti *et al.*, 2016). The selection of a crop for rotation is very important as species that enhance Nitrogen in the soil can increase the phyto-mass production of the subsequent crops and consequently increase the soil organic matter (Raphael *et al.*, 2016). Thus, increasing the soil organic matter is a sustainable method to enhance crop productivity as well as increase the carbon sequestration and maintaining global carbon-cycle.

Cover cropping is a sustainable approach for enhancing soil health, soil microbial biomass and agro-ecosystem services such as nutrient cycling, water storage, weed and pest control and carbon sequestration (Pinto *et al.*, 2017). Cover crop refers to the crop that is grown to cover the ground for reducing soil erosion and nutrient loss.

Cover crops can be harvested before planting of the main crops or they can be grown alongside the main crop to provide living mulch (Robacer *et al.*, 2016). According to FAO (2011), cover crops are sustainable farming tool that increase soil organic matter and improve soil water dynamics (Duval *et al.*, 2016). They are recognized as green manure and add nitrogen to the agro-ecosystem either by fixation or by improving the Nitrogen mineralization, consequently declining synthetic fertilizers inputs and their resultant green-house emissions (Alvarez *et al.*, 2017). Grass and legume cover crops are recognized as the sustainable tool to supporting nutrient cycling and conserving water and soil resources (Jahanzada *et al.*, 2017). However, legume cover cropping is commonly practiced by smallholder farmers in tropics.

Organic compost is a sustainable and climate-smart approach to increase soil fertility. Composting refers to the natural process of rotting or decomposition of organic matter by microorganisms under controlled conditions. Thus, it is a bio-chemical process in which microbial degradation of organic waste results into a product known as organic manure or compost (Onwosi *et al.*, 2017).

Composting is a sustainable approach for organic waste management. Variety of organic materials are used in composting process such as straw, crop residues, agroindustry by-products, livestock waste, sewage sludge and kitchen waste (Proietti *et al.*, 2016). Organic composting process begins with putting the organic waste into a pit for several days or

months. The heap of organic waste undergoes microbial degradation that converts organic waste into compost.

Women farmers and income generation

In Niger, rural women are at the forefront of agricultural production, processing, distribution and sale of food and food products, as well as the core of household feeding. Nevertheless, they have restricted access to productive resources such as land, agricultural inputs, finance, credit, extension services and technology, and this limits their agricultural outputs (FAO, 2023).

A work carried out in Tanzania aimed to examine women's productive roles in household food and income in the 2019/20 and 2020/21 cropping seasons and associated factors among crop farmers and agropastoralists revealed that women make up half of the global workforce in both agricultural and non-agricultural sectors to provide household food and income (Mtagulwa and Hadijah, 2024).

The World Bank (2016) also made gender equity in the agriculture and food sector a specific goal and is working to expand women's access to land and rural finance. Feed the Future programme of the U.S. government on global hunger and food-security have helped nearly 2.4 million women improve their agricultural production and acquired food-security-related skills. It has helped more than 420,000 women access agriculture-related credit (International Food Policy and Research Institute (IFPRI), 2017).

In Nigeria, women constitute 75% of agricultural workforce in Nigeria yet suffer marginalisation in accessing information and resources (Ifeanyi-Obi, 2023). Despite the fact that they are more exposed and vulnerable to climate change, they are less represented in climate change initiatives in the country hence their needs scarcely addressed.

Given women's responsibilities for household work, it is surprising to know they could produce most of the food. If women had the same access to productive resources as men, they could increase yields on their farms by 20 to 30 percent. This could raise total agricultural output in developing countries by 2.5 to 4 percent, which could in turn reduce the number of hungry people in the world by 12 to 17 percent (Doss, 2018). Apart producing staple crops, women farmers engage in diverse income generating activities in order to ensure their household food security.

Ayanwuyi and Akintonde (2011) reported that on-farm income activities engaged by most women in their study area to support household food security includes weeding, gathering of wood and non-wood forest products, land clearing, planting/transplanting, fertilizer application, transport of farm produce for household consumption, crop harvesting, crop processing and chemical application. Increase in women's income generation had significantly higher impact on household food security compared to a similar increase in men's income. In the developing world, women use almost all of their income to cover the family's needs,

while men spend at least 25% on other uses (FAO, 2010).

Onyebu (2016) defines income generation to simply mean gaining or increasing income or money that an individual or business receives in exchange for providing a good or service after investing capital. Income generating activities focus on productively using locally available resources to the benefit of the entire community. In the strict sense of the term, income generation aims at creating a financial income, however, may also aim at positive effects in terms of self-reliance, household satisfaction, empowerment and community development as a whole (Yusuf *et al.*, 2015).

Overview of food crops production in Nigeria and women involvement

Agriculture has been the basic source of subsistence for human societies. Food and Agricultural Organization (2007) reported that the quantity of food produced per capita has been declining since 1984 as the population is increasing in alarming rate. Studies have shown that women produce over 50 per cent of all food grown worldwide (FAO, 2011). In most of the developing nation including Nigeria, the face of farming is female. Global reports by the United Nations' Food and Agriculture Organization (UN-FAO) indicated that majority of economically active women in the least-developed countries work in agriculture. Major food crops produced by women include beans, sesame, cassava, groundnuts, maize (corn), melon, millet, rice, sorghum, soybeans and yams.

Food crop production remains a central aim of most smallholder farmers that dominated Nigeria agricultural sector (Daudu *et al.*, 2019). According to Maurice *et al.* (2013) food crop production in Nigeria is dominated by small-scale farmers who cultivate between 0.1 to 5.99 hectares and produce about 85-90% of the total foods consumed in the country. Unfortunately, these small-scale farmers are subsistence and use crude or traditional production techniques. They are further constrained by inadequate finance to expand production, hence rely on personal savings for their agricultural operations.

Daudu *et al.* (2017) posited that small holder women farmers are less involved in soil fertility management practices that are critical to food crop production. They are also confronted with problems like access to credits, resource inputs and extension information than their men counterparts. Since, both men and women are responsible for production of food crops in Nigeria, men have always been seen as dominants and this assumption undermines women's participation in agricultural activities. Women's contribution to agricultural production varies from country to country, crop to crop and task to task (Marilee, 2009). Women perform many tasks in household crop production, including sowing seeds, weeding, applying fertilizers and pesticides, harvesting and threshing of the crops. They are also responsible for post-harvest food processing, storage, transport and marketing. Ayanwuyi and Akintunde (2011) reported that food crops produced by most of the rural women in their

study area are maize, yam cassava and cowpea production implying that women in the study area are into production of major staple food crops.

Women are farmers and food producers. They produce a large part of the world's food (Bassey, 2015). Karl (2009) reported that exact data on women participation in food crops production is very hard to come by, while FAO (2009) estimated that about 50 to 60% women are the main producers of the world's staple foods like maize, wheat and rice. Dauda (2009) reported that women provide up to 90 per cent of the labour for rice cultivation in south-Western Nigeria. They are mostly found producing food crops for their families and local markets, and sometimes also found in agricultural wage labour.

3.0 CONCLUSION

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The level of involvement of rural women in food crop production and income generation in Nigeria is very low. Effective and efficient execution of household and farm roles by women requires quick access to farm and off-farm resources, which is usually not the case because of social and technical constraints. In Nigeria, women's contribution to food crops production is relegated to the background as more attention is being centred on the male gender. Several agricultural development programmes focused on the role played by male gender in food crop production at the expense of women in terms of extension information and services delivery such as inputs (fertilizers, seeds) and credit. The need arises, therefore, to consider the participation of rural women for the effectiveness of sustainable food crop production strategies for improved income generation in Nigeria.

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